

Bachelor's Thesis

Neural Simulations and Brain-Computer Interfaces;
Algorithmic Challenges and Future Perspectives

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Abstract

Brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) and neural simulations represent a significant advancement at the intersection of neuroscience, artificial intelligence, and computer science. This thesis aims to explore their technical foundations, both medical and non-medical applications, as well as the challenges they currently pose and those anticipated in the future.

First, we will define what BCIs are and analyze their applications, focusing on motor and cognitive rehabilitation. We will also examine current limitations of these technologies, particularly regarding precision, accessibility, and reliability. Then, we will explore brain signal acquisition methods, such as electroencephalography (EEG), magnetoencephalography (MEG), and invasive implants, while examining signal processing algorithms and neural modeling required to interpret these signals. Special attention will be given to computational models and machine learning techniques—especially artificial intelligence—designed to optimize these interfaces.

Neural simulations will also be studied, including their principles and applications in computing, especially in modeling brain circuits and their integration into human-machine interaction systems. We will then examine their connection with artificial intelligence and their role in developing immersive technologies.

Finally, we will address the ethical and security issues of BCIs, emphasizing the protection of brain data and the societal repercussions of these technologies. A reflection will be conducted on the future of BCIs and neural simulations, including upcoming technological advances and the feasibility of full sensory immersion, inspired by science fiction.

This thesis thus aims to provide a comprehensive and critical vision of BCIs and neural simulations, highlighting their potential, limitations, and future implications.

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Introduction

Brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) establish a direct communication pathway between the brain and an external device by merging neuroscience, computer science, and artificial intelligence. Initially designed for medical applications such as motor rehabilitation, these interfaces are now being explored in areas like entertainment, education, and augmented reality.

The Wolpaw duo [1] (Wolpaw, J. & Wolpaw, E. W., 2012) present the fundamental principles of BCIs, from neurobiological foundations to neural signal processing techniques. [7] Lebedev and Nicolelis (2006) distinguish between two categories of BCIs: invasive devices, which involve intracranial implants (offering high precision but requiring surgical intervention), and non-invasive devices (like EEG or MEG), which are more accessible but less accurate.

BCI research faces several challenges: improving signal quality, reducing invasiveness, integrating artificial intelligence, and addressing ethical and security concerns. For instance, [44] Saha et al. (2021) emphasize the role of machine learning in optimizing brain signal processing and reducing decoding errors. At the same time, public awareness initiatives such as [42] BrainFacts.org and [43] The BCI Guy highlight the importance of protecting brain data and the potential misuse of these technologies. This thesis provides a multifaceted analysis of BCIs, covering the current state of the art, brain signal acquisition and processing methods, neural simulations, ethical challenges, and future prospects.

1. Brain-Computer Interfaces: State of the Art

1.1 Definition and Classification of Brain-Computer Interfaces

Brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) are technological systems that translate neural activity into commands usable by a computer or mechanical system, without using traditional neural or muscular pathways. They allow individuals to interact with an external environment purely through thought, via three key steps: capturing brain activity, decoding it (signal processing), and executing a corresponding action or response.

Figure 1 – Diagram of a brain-computer interface (BCI).

The neural signal is recorded, processed by a computer system (AI and neural networks), and used to control a robotic arm via a visual feedback loop.

Classification by Invasiveness

BCIs fall into two categories:

- **Invasive Interfaces:** Requiring surgical opening of the skull to place electrodes directly on the cortex, this method provides the highest signal quality—detecting individual neuron activity for precise control of, for example, prosthetic limbs. However, this approach carries risks such as hemorrhage, infection, or bodily rejection. It is typically reserved for research or very specific clinical cases. Neuralink ([9] Kaushik et al., 2021) is a pioneer in this field, achieving safer and more robust capture of hundreds of simultaneous neural signals.
- **Non-Invasive Interfaces:** These methods measure brain activity using sensors placed on the scalp. EEG (electroencephalography) is the most widely used technique due to its low cost, portability, and high temporal resolution ([8] Nicolas-Alonso & Gomez-Gil, 2012). Other techniques include MEG (magnetoencephalography) or fNIRS (near-infrared spectroscopy), which are more complex and costly. The main drawback of non-invasive methods is their lower precision, as they often generalize over regions rather than capturing unit-specific activity, and are susceptible to interference or noise in the results.

Classification by Direction of Information

BCIs are also classified based on the direction of information flow:

- **Unidirectional BCIs:** Information flows from the brain to the machine. This is the classical use case, where motor intent is decoded to control a cursor or robotic arm.
- **Bidirectional BCIs:** These systems add sensory feedback to the brain, often through electrical or haptic stimulation. This allows the user to perceive the machine's response, creating a more natural control loop. These systems are promising but still experimental.

Classification by Cognitive Use

BCIs can also be categorized by the user's cognitive engagement:

- **Active:** Requires explicit intention from the user (e.g., imagining a movement).
- **Reactive:** Uses responses to external stimuli (e.g., P300, SSVEP).
- **Passive:** Monitors mental states without specific intention (e.g., stress or fatigue detection).

Neuroscientific Foundations

BCI performance relies on brain adaptability through learning (neural plasticity), which allows users to improve interface control over time. According to [21] Kandel et al. (2021), this brain plasticity is crucial to mastering a BCI. BCIs are evolving into increasingly adaptive systems—shifting from basic transmitter/receiver models to interactive ones. [29] Lebedev & Nicolelis (2017) indicate that artificial intelligence can dynamically adjust interface parameters to match the user's abilities and context, reducing user effort and improving precision.

This field offers highly promising prospects for both clinical applications (neuroprosthetics, rehabilitation) and societal impact, while raising critical ethical and security questions due to its multidisciplinary nature.

1.2 Medical Applications of BCIs

The earliest BCI applications were developed in the medical field, primarily to restore motor functions in patients suffering from severe disabilities such as paralysis, amputation, ALS (amyotrophic lateral sclerosis), or stroke. A notable example is Stephen Hawking, whose wheelchair was enhanced through BCI technology. These applications allow paralyzed or amputated individuals to regain a degree of autonomy by controlling devices or interfaces using their thoughts.

A particularly notable case in recent years, alongside Neuralink, is that of the company **Synchron**, featured in a [41] Bloomberg Technology video. They designed a miniature invasive brain implant capable of transmitting neural signals, allowing patients to control nearby devices. These technologies have been tested on paralyzed individuals, enabling them to interact with a computer or send messages. Noland Arbaugh, a patient using Neuralink, is a prime example of these advancements.

[29] Lebedev & Nicolelis (2017) explain the scientific foundations and early clinical results of BCIs in neuroprosthetics and neurological rehabilitation. Additionally, the study by [31] Nijboer et al. (2010) introduces another dimension: the psychological state of the patient (motivation, fatigue, stress) significantly influences the effectiveness of neural signal decoding. In this perspective, it appears that BCIs not only rely on decoding algorithms but also require user engagement through neural feedback systems. [8] Nicolas-Alonso & Gomez-Gil (2012) highlight how such systems can stimulate brain plasticity after a stroke by reinforcing weakened connections.

From a philosophical standpoint, [9] Glannon (2021) questions the boundary between restoration and cognitive enhancement. When BCIs enhance abilities beyond the human norm, they challenge our understanding of personal identity, informed consent, and raise ethical concerns about human-machine hybridization. These issues are echoed by [10] Kaushik et al. (2021) in discussions around Neuralink.

In conclusion, medical BCIs have already crossed significant milestones in clinical settings, but their implementation raises ongoing concerns regarding ethics, accessibility, long-term reliability, and their impact on patients.

1.3 Current Limitations of BCIs in Medical and Non-Medical Fields

Despite recent advances and promising results in both clinical and technological domains, brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) face numerous limitations that hinder their widespread adoption.

Technical Limitations

Signal reliability remains a significant challenge. Non-invasive methods like EEG are highly sensitive to external noise and suffer from low spatial resolution, limiting command precision. In addition to this instability, inter-individual variability complicates the creation of universal models, requiring long and highly specific calibration for each user ([12] Nicolas-Alonso & Gomez-Gil, 2012).

On the invasive side, while implants offer higher precision, they face issues such as biocompatibility, long-term degradation, and high costs. These constraints restrict their use to strictly medical or experimental contexts ([29] Lebedev & Nicolelis, 2017; [10] Kaushik et al., 2021).

Ethical and Legal Limitations

The confidentiality of brain data is a major concern. Signals extracted from the brain can potentially reveal sensitive information about an individual's emotions, intentions, or cognitive states. [9] Glannon (2021) stresses the need for strict regulation to govern the use, storage, and transmission of such data. The concept of neurosecurity has thus emerged as a distinct research field, aiming to prevent hacking or manipulation of these highly personal signals.

Limitations in Non-Medical Domains

In non-clinical contexts, BCIs generate strong interest—particularly in video games, immersive environments, and education. However, current BCI technology is still poorly suited for fluid and immersive use. [30] Nijholt et al. (2009) note issues such as latency, low bandwidth, and control complexity that slow their adoption. Moreover, the absence of industrial standards, high costs, and general public unawareness limit their expansion beyond the medical field.

Toward Gradual Adoption

BCIs remain a promising technology, but their democratization will depend on continuous technical improvement, robust regulatory frameworks, and deep ethical reflection. The following chapters will delve into the scientific and computational foundations necessary to optimize these systems.

2. Brain Signal Acquisition and Processing

2.1. Acquisition Methods: EEG, MEG, Invasive Implants, etc.

Brain signal acquisition is central to the operation of brain-computer interfaces (BCIs). It enables the capture of neural activity and its transformation into commands via a computing system. The three main acquisition methods are electroencephalography (EEG), magnetoencephalography (MEG), and intracranial implants.

Electroencephalography (EEG)

EEG is a non-invasive technique that records potential variations generated by neural populations via electrodes placed on the scalp. It is widely used in BCIs due to its low cost, portability, and high temporal resolution, making it ideal for real-time applications such as rehabilitation, gaming, and object control.

However, it has low spatial resolution, and signals are susceptible to interference (e.g., movement, blinking, muscle activity), requiring rigorous signal preprocessing ([25] Chanoine et al., 2014).

Magnetoencephalography (MEG)

MEG captures the magnetic fields generated by neural activity. Unlike EEG, it is less affected by brain tissue and provides better localization of neural sources, while maintaining high temporal resolution ([28] Hämäläinen et al., 1993).

Nonetheless, MEG is expensive, requires cryogenic sensors and shielded environments, and lacks portability—limiting its use primarily to clinical research.

Intracranial Implants

Electrodes implanted directly in or on the cortex provide the highest precision recordings, including single-neuron action potentials ([27] Buzsáki, 2004). These implants are especially used to control prosthetics or robotic arms requiring high signal accuracy.

However, they involve major surgery and carry risks such as infection, inflammation, or rejection.

Summary

Figure 2 – Comparison between EEG and MEG.

EEG measures electrical potentials while MEG detects magnetic fields, with notable differences in spatial resolution.

The choice of acquisition method is a trade-off between precision, cost, comfort, and medical risk. While EEG remains the most accessible technology, implants offer the most advanced performance—at the cost of complexity. MEG is mostly limited to research. Future advances in hybrid systems or next-generation sensors (flexible, miniaturized, biocompatible) could make BCIs more effective and widely available.

2.2. Neural Modeling: Basic Principles and Associated Technologies

Neural modeling is an essential component in the functioning of brain-computer interfaces (BCIs), as it allows for the representation, simulation, and exploitation of brain activity to better decode intentions or mental states. It relies on mathematical and computational approaches that aim to reproduce the behavior of neurons and the dynamics of the networks in which they interact.

Fundamental Principles

Neural models simulate properties such as:

- **Synaptic integration**, which sums incoming signals;
- **Excitability**, which determines the threshold for triggering an action potential;
- **Synaptic plasticity**, which allows connections to adapt based on learning;
- **Reinforcement learning**, based on reward feedback signals.

[20] Dayan & Abbott (2001), in *Theoretical Neuroscience*, describe various model types: from simple models like integrate-and-fire to complex biophysical models such as Hodgkin-Huxley. These models can be applied at different levels of granularity, from single neurons to entire neural populations. In BCIs, they are used to anticipate motor intentions and calibrate real-time decoding algorithms.

Structure and Organization of Neural Networks

Beyond the behavior of individual neurons, it is essential to model the collective functioning of neural networks. [26] Sporns & Kötter (2004) propose an approach based on recurrent patterns (functional motifs) in brain architecture. These motifs are repeated configurations of neural connections (triads, cycles, modules) that facilitate specific information processing (filtering, anticipation, synchronization).

This logic also aligns with the study of the connectome, i.e., the mapping of neural connections. Its analysis helps in designing better-suited computational architectures for tasks such as EEG signal classification in BCIs.

Applications in BCIs

In brain-computer interfaces, these models allow for:

- Simulating expected activity to calibrate a neural decoder;
- Creating artificial neural network architectures inspired by biological ones;
- Enhancing AI performance through finer modeling of decision systems.

In short, neural modeling bridges fundamental neuroscience and advanced computational applications, improving both our understanding of the brain and the technical performance of BCIs.

2.3. Algorithms for Brain Signal Processing and Interpretation

Figure 3 – Functional diagram of a BCI integrating artificial intelligence

This diagram illustrates the data flow in a modern brain-computer interface, including signal acquisition, feature extraction, AI-based interpretation, and command execution for external systems (e.g., EEG headset, virtual reality apps, connected devices, etc.)

Processing brain signals is a core function of BCIs, aiming to extract actionable information from raw neural activity to control external systems. This process involves three main stages: preprocessing, feature extraction, and classification.

Preprocessing and Pattern Detection

EEG, MEG, or intracranial signals are naturally noisy and complex. Preprocessing eliminates artifacts such as eye movements, blinking, or muscle activity, and standardizes the data. This step enables identification of specific neural patterns associated with particular intentions.

Commonly used techniques include the Fourier transform and wavelet decomposition ([25] Chanoine et al., 2014), which extract usable temporal and spectral features.

Machine Learning and Classification

Once features are extracted, classification algorithms link this data to the user's intentions or mental states. These methods can be:

- **Supervised** (e.g., support vector machines, neural networks, random forests), or
- **Unsupervised** (e.g., k-means, hierarchical clustering).

Recent advances in machine learning and deep learning have significantly improved decoding accuracy and robustness, enabling systems to better adapt to individual variations in brain signals.

Large-Scale Recording and Decoding

According to [27] Buzsáki (2004), simultaneous recording of large neural populations provides better insight into global brain dynamics. Integrating this data into advanced models enhances decoding relevance and effectiveness—critical for real-time applications such as prosthetics or neurofeedback.

Toward Adaptive BCIs

Modern approaches aim for intelligent systems that adapt to the user. By combining neural modeling techniques (see section 2.2) with adaptive algorithms, we can develop BCIs sensitive to cognitive or emotional states, thus enhancing the fluidity and personalization of interactions.

In conclusion, the efficiency of a BCI depends as much on signal quality as on the relevance of the algorithms used. Advances in signal processing and artificial intelligence are paving the way for more responsive, accurate, and versatile systems.

3. Neural Simulations: Principles and Applications

3.1. Definition and Functioning of Neural Simulations

Neural simulations replicate the functioning of the brain using mathematical and computational models. They play a central role in BCIs by helping to understand neural dynamics, test neuroscientific hypotheses, and optimize decoding algorithms.

Objectives of Neural Simulations

These simulations can be used for :

- Understand the dynamics of neural networks (e.g., synchronization, information propagation);
- Test scenarios that are difficult to observe in vivo;
- Optimize BCI design by simulating neural responses to stimuli or conditions;
- Guide training of artificial neural networks by drawing from biological principles.

Computational Models of Neurons

[3] Izhikevich (2007) describes neurons as dynamic oscillators capable of a wide range of behaviors (bursting, rhythmic firing, adaptation). These biologically realistic models are implemented in tools such as NEURON or Brian2, which are widely used in computational neuroscience.

Figure 4 – "Integrate-and-Fire" model

The neuron integrates incoming current until it crosses an excitability threshold; an action potential is then triggered, followed by a refractory period.

Artificial Neural Networks and Learning

[37] Thuillier (1997) describes artificial neural networks as systems inspired by the brain, capable of classification or prediction through learning algorithms (supervised or unsupervised). Their effectiveness increases with techniques like gradient backpropagation.

Relevance for BCIs

These models play a dual role in the context of BCIs:

- Helping understand brain functions—such as learning mechanisms, plasticity, or neural coding;
- Improving signal decoding and interpretation algorithms by drawing inspiration from biological networks.

Neural simulations thus establish a theoretical and technical bridge between neuroscience and artificial intelligence—two essential pillars of next-generation BCIs.

3.2. Computational Applications of Neural Simulations

Neural simulations go beyond fundamental research and now have concrete applications in computing, signal processing, artificial intelligence, BCIs, and immersive environments.

Enhancing Decoding Capabilities

[15] Ribeiro & Gosselin (2018) demonstrate that artificial neural networks inspired by biological mechanisms improve the detection and interpretation of brain signals. These adaptive models, trained on large EEG/MEG datasets, can accurately identify specific neural patterns linked to mental intentions or activities. They enable the design of more robust, precise, and personalized brain-computer interfaces that better accommodate individual variability.

Bio-Inspired Models for Frugal AI

Given the growing resource demands of traditional AI models, [36] Muzy (2022) proposes a bio-inspired approach that mimics brain mechanisms—such as synaptic plasticity or local learning—to build energy-efficient yet powerful neural networks. These "frugal" models are especially suited for complex tasks like real-time neural decoding or sensory feedback in BCIs.

Numerical Simulation and Hybrid AI

According to [39] Inria (2022), hybridizing numerical simulations with AI allows for combining physical models of neural propagation with machine learning algorithms. This improves predictive accuracy while ensuring greater interpretability. In BCIs, it facilitates the development of robust neural decoders capable of adapting to real-life conditions (e.g., signal fluctuations, movement artifacts, cognitive changes).

Applications in Immersive Environments

[38] SkillCo (2023) also emphasizes the value of adaptive algorithms in virtual reality environments. By providing dynamic and realistic responses to user interactions, these technologies significantly enhance the user experience, with applications in entertainment, professional training, and medical rehabilitation.

In summary, neural simulations actively contribute to the development of smarter, more adaptive, and resource-efficient technologies—especially within brain-computer interfaces and immersive systems.

3.3. Connections with Immersive Systems and Artificial Intelligence

Neural simulations, when combined with artificial intelligence (AI), greatly expand the potential of immersive technologies. They move beyond simple brain modeling to enable sophisticated, dynamic human-machine interactions.

AI Serving Immersion

As noted by [38] SkillCo (2023), integrating machine learning algorithms allows immersive environments to adapt in real time to the user's cognitive and behavioral state. This dynamic adaptability significantly enhances the user experience in several domains:

- **Virtual Reality (VR):** More natural interactions through continuous analysis of brain signals.

- **Augmented Reality (AR):** Adaptive overlay of relevant information based on cognitive states.
- **Training and Rehabilitation:** Exercises tailored to the user’s evolving brain activity and learning patterns.

Toward a BCI–AI–Immersion Synergy

The synergy between BCIs, AI, and neural simulations opens the door to innovative applications, including:

- Thought-controlled video games that respond to the player’s emotions and attention level.
- Immersive medical systems effective in treating pain, phobias, or motor disorders.
- Telepresence environments that integrate realistic sensory feedback based on brain activity.

These adaptive neural models improve system responsiveness, fluidity, and personalization—key aspects for user acceptance and effectiveness.

A Technological Convergence

The convergence of neuroscience, bio-inspired AI ([36] Muzy, 2022), and digital immersion points to the emergence of personalized sensory experiences—capable of anticipating and responding in real time to user needs.

Bio-inspired models, which are energy-efficient, facilitate the realization of total sensory immersion, bringing today’s technology closer to science fiction scenarios ([37] Thuillier, 1997; [38] SkillCo, 2023).

In the future, BCIs could interact actively with users in intelligent environments that are seamless—and potentially indistinguishable—from reality.

4. Ethical and Security Challenges of BCI Technologies

4.1. Privacy and Protection of Brain Data

While brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) offer new opportunities for communication and control, they also raise significant ethical concerns—particularly around privacy. Unlike conventional biometric data, neural signals can reveal deeply personal information about a person’s thoughts, emotions, or intentions, sometimes without their awareness ([19] Ienca & Haselager, 2016).

Risks of Misuse and Hacking

As BCIs become increasingly connected, the risk of “brain hacking” grows. This includes unauthorized access, cognitive manipulation, and neural identity theft. With the spread of intracranial or real-time connected devices, such threats are becoming more plausible—posing serious risks to users’ privacy and mental integrity ([19] Ienca & Haselager, 2016).

Figure 5 – Hacking risks in BCIs

The diagram illustrates potential vulnerabilities in neural signal processing: malicious feature extraction, hijacked classification algorithms, or manipulated sensory feedback.

Toward New Neuroethical Rights

In response, [18] Ienca & Andorno (2017) propose a set of new human rights for the age of neurotechnology:

- **Cognitive liberty:** Protection from external influence without consent.
- **Mental privacy:** Ban on accessing thoughts without explicit permission.
- **Mental integrity:** Safeguards against non-consensual cognitive manipulation.

These proposals aim to address the urgent need for regulation as neural devices become more common in medical, military, and recreational settings.

A Legal and Technological Imperative

To protect users effectively, BCI developers must integrate advanced security protocols from the design phase—such as strong encryption for brain data and dynamic consent systems. At the same time, a specific legal framework must be created to safeguard fundamental rights in this new cognitive domain.

In conclusion, the rise of BCI technologies demands rigorous ethical reflection and robust legal and technical safeguards to ensure the privacy and security of brain data.

4.2. Social Implications of BCIs

The growing use of brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) outside the medical context raises major questions about social equity, human identity, and individual autonomy.

Unequal Access to Neurotechnology

The high costs and technical complexity of BCIs risk deepening social divides. Broad adoption of these technologies could create a cognitively “augmented” elite, reinforcing inequalities in employment, education, and beyond—introducing a form of digital cognitively based discrimination.

Transformations of Identity and Free Will

Direct connections between mental activity and technology challenge the very notion of cognitive autonomy. In *The Hacker Crackdown* ([23] Sterling, 1992), the author explores tensions between individual freedom and technological control in cyberspace. Applied to BCIs, this concern becomes even more intimate: the brain becomes a digital territory, potentially subject to surveillance or manipulation.

Sociotechnical Risks and Cognitive Dependence

Widespread BCI adoption could lead to cognitive dependency, with essential mental functions like memory or attention outsourced to machines. This poses a risk of weakening natural capabilities in the event of technical failure. Furthermore, rigid cognitive norms could emerge in sensitive fields like education or employment—threatening mental diversity and individual freedom.

In summary, the social implications of BCIs go far beyond technical challenges. They profoundly reshape our relationship to technology, to others, and to ourselves.

4.3. Special Cases: Futuristic Visions and Science Fiction Examples

Science fiction is a powerful tool for exploring the social, ethical, and identity-related consequences of brain-computer interfaces (BCIs). Through futuristic scenarios, it anticipates both the potential benefits and the possible dangers of these technologies.

Total Immersion and Cyberspace

In *Neuromancer* ([24] Gibson, 1984), BCIs offer complete cognitive immersion in cyberspace, fusing the human mind with digital networks. The novel highlights the risks of digital dependency and the erosion of boundaries between the real and the virtual—foreshadowing projects like those from Neuralink.

Identity, Humanity, and Artificial Consciousness

In *Do Androids Dream of Electric Sheep?* ([22] Dick, 1968), the central question is the boundary between human and machine. Androids exhibit cognitive and emotional capabilities similar to humans, challenging the very definition of consciousness. Here, BCIs are implicitly evoked as technologies that enable emotional simulation or manipulation of perceived reality.

These narratives provoke essential questions: If a machine can feel or simulate human experience via a neural interface, what does that mean for our own humanity? Can we be reduced to a brain signal?

Foresight Tools for Emerging Technologies

Science fiction plays a key role in current ethical debates on BCIs by imagining possible futures. Though sometimes dystopian, these works raise questions that technology alone tends to ignore:

- What does it mean to be constantly connected?
- Can consciousness be simulated?
- Who owns mental data in a world where the mind is a resource?

In summary, these fictional works act as critical mirrors to guide the development of BCIs—reminding us that behind every innovation lie deep human issues that must be anticipated now.

5. Future Perspectives and Potential Advances

5.1. Technical Improvements in BCIs

Recent developments in brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) aim to make these systems faster, more accurate, and suitable for daily use.

Optimizing Signal Acquisition

As noted by [8] Nicolas-Alonso & Gomez-Gil (2012), improvements in brain signal acquisition (EEG, MEG, invasive implants) include:

- Increased sensor density for better spatial resolution;
- Reduced electromagnetic noise;
- More reliable, biocompatible materials for implants;
- Lightweight, user-friendly portable EEG headsets for daily applications.

Artificial Intelligence and Neural Decoding

The integration of AI and deep learning now allows fast and precise detection of user intentions and cognitive states. These bio-inspired models facilitate the real-time dynamic adaptation of BCIs—enhancing their responsiveness and personalization.

Toward Everyday Use

Future developments focus on:

- Significantly reducing calibration time;
- Advanced automation of signal processing;
- Improved spatiotemporal resolution.

These technical advances mark a major step toward intuitive interaction and widespread integration of BCIs in everyday life.

5.2. Development of Immersive and Non-Medical Applications

Brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) are rapidly expanding into diverse areas such as entertainment, education, art, and sports, relying on the real-time interpretation of mental activity ([32] Nijholt et al., 2022).

Diversifying Uses Beyond the Clinical Field

BCIs now enable:

- Intuitive control of video games through thought;
- Emotional interaction with interactive art installations;
- Enhanced athletic performance through personalized neural feedback;
- Dynamic adaptation of educational content based on attention or cognitive fatigue.

These applications aim to make human–machine interaction more natural and adaptive.

Figure 6 – Diagram of a BCI connected to a virtual reality environment

Brain activity (EEG) is translated into commands for interacting with virtual scenes and objects. The system delivers visual, auditory, and haptic feedback to strengthen immersion.

Optimizing Immersion and Responsiveness

Despite current technical challenges—such as low EEG resolution or processing delays ([30] Nijholt et al., 2009)—advanced AI algorithms and multisensor fusion are significantly improving the fluidity and realism of immersive interactions ([40] Cummings & Bailenson, 2016).

Toward Everyday BCIs

As they move beyond the clinical context, BCIs are opening the door to new types of interaction in connected daily life: immersive games, interactive museums, emotional interfaces, adaptive personal assistants, etc. The challenge will be to balance ethics, accessibility, and technical rigor to offer robust, secure, and genuinely useful solutions for everyday use.

5.3. Reflection on Total Immersion: Long-Term Challenges

Total immersion, where users experience a virtual world indistinguishable from reality, is an ambitious goal of BCI technologies—frequently explored in science fiction (e.g., *Sword Art Online*, [6] Kawahara, 2009). However, achieving this scenario presents significant technical, physiological, and ethical challenges.

Complete Sensory Immersion

Current immersive technologies only partially simulate human senses (vision, hearing, touch). Achieving full immersion would require:

- **Multisensory stimulation**, including proprioception and simulated pain;
- **Deep, stable, and secure neural integration** over the long term.

Technical and Physiological Challenges

Systems must protect users from the negative effects of prolonged use, including immobility, cognitive overload, or perceptual disturbances ([40] Cummings & Bailenson, 2016).

Ethical and Societal Issues

This type of technology raises deep questions about consciousness, free will, and the boundary between real and virtual:

- Is it ethically acceptable for individuals to prefer virtual life over reality?
- Who owns and controls the associated brain data?

A Plausible Future Reality?

Despite the challenges, the rapid advances in BCIs and AI make increasingly complete immersion a real possibility. However, a strict regulatory framework and deep ethical reflection will be essential to ensure that these developments remain beneficial and respectful of individual liberties.

6. Conclusion and perspectives

Brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) represent a major advancement at the crossroads of neuroscience, artificial intelligence, and numerical simulation. Their rapid evolution suggests a profound transformation in human interaction across medical, social, educational, and immersive domains.

A Broad and Promising Potential

Already used to restore motor and cognitive functions in patients, BCIs could also revolutionize learning, entertainment, and artistic creation. As Michio Kaku [5] (2014) imagines, directly connecting thoughts to the digital world opens unprecedented possibilities—but also requires rigorous ethical considerations.

Major Ethical and Societal Issues

The protection of brain data and the preservation of cognitive liberty are central concerns. Risks of cognitive manipulation or mental surveillance demand a clear regulatory framework, supported by thorough neuroethical reflection.

Ambitious Yet Uncertain Immersive Future

Total immersion—long imagined in science fiction—remains out of reach for now, with significant technical, physiological, and ethical barriers. However, current progress will soon enable highly adaptive and personalized experiences, redefining our relationship with the body, the mind, and technology.

In conclusion

BCIs are no longer just experimental technologies; they represent a true societal issue. For them to fully benefit the common good, their democratization must be supported by responsible governance—one that protects mental integrity, individual freedom, and guarantees ethical, inclusive, and transparent use.

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